

EUDAIMONIA: THE NEXUS OF PHYSICAL-MENTAL WELLNESS & ADDITIONAL FOUR DIMENSIONS OF WELLNESS

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Everyone knows what physical wellness or health (both terms are used interchangeably throughout this article) is. Another term for it is physical fitness, i.e., a state of health and well-being. To be more specific, it refers to the ability to perform aspects of sports, occupations and activities of daily living. Physical wellness can be attained through three key ways: (1) proper nutrition (Healy & Owen, 2010); (2) moderately vigorous physical exercises (de Groot & Fagerstrom, 2011); and (3) adequate rest (Malina, 2010) together with a formal recovery program, if any, prepared by a health professional.

Another familiar term is mental wellness or health. This encompasses one's socio-emotional and psychological well-being, influencing cognition, perception, and behavior. Mental wellness affects how a person thinks, feels, and/or acts (CDC, 2023). Mental wellness also concerns about how one manages stress or copes with it (including anxiety and depression, if any), interacts with others, and also makes decisions or other healthy choices.

Definition of Wellness

The key word here is wellness, whose origin can be traced back to the ancient Greek term eudaimonia, which, in turn, probably means "flourishing". The Greek philosopher Aristotle (b.384 BC–d.322 BC) described eudaimonia as a broad concept referring to the highest good humans could strive toward: a life 'well lived' or living virtuously.

The Global Wellness Institute (2010) has defined wellness in terms of a person's active pursuit of activities, choices and lifestyles leading to a state of holistic health. According to DeHaan and Ryan (2014), from the self-determination perspective, there are two dominating traditional theories of wellness about pathways to happiness and the good life: "(1) The hedonic tradition focuses on happiness as a desired subjective outcome, with interest in variables predicting it. (2) The eudaimonic tradition focuses on characteristics associated with living well, defined in terms of realization of human potentials,

and views happiness as one by-product of such living" (p. 37).

More recently, Pappadopoulos (2023) has defined wellness (or eudaimonia) as "the act of practicing healthy habits on a daily basis to attain better physical and mental health outcomes, so that instead of just surviving, one is thriving" (para. 1). Hence, in order to understand the significance of wellness, it is important for everyone also to understand how wellness is linked to health (Pappadopoulos, 2023).

Dimensions of Wellness

Perhaps one of the most known models of wellness comes from Hettler (1984), the founder of the National Wellness Institute based in Wisconsin, USA. He proposed his model of six interdependent dimensions: (1) physical with a combination of exercise and eating habits; (2) emotional with an awareness and acceptance of feelings; (3) social with contribution to environment and community; (4) spiritual with the search for meaning and purpose in life; (5) intellectual including creative and stimulating activities; and (6) occupational relating to personal satisfaction and enrichment in life through work (see Figure 1).

However, Stoewen (2017) argued there are eight mutually interdependent dimensions of wellness: (1) physical, (2) intellectual, (3) emotional, (4) social, (5) spiritual, (6) vocational, (7) financial, and (8) environmental (see Figure 2). She argued that "attention must be given to all the dimensions, as neglect of any one over time will adversely

affect the others, and ultimately one's health, well-being, and quality of life" (Stoewen, 2017, p. 861). In this way, an individual's personal harmony can be attained. For this reason, Stoewen (2017) emphasized that wellness necessitates a good self-stewardship, for oneself as well as those whom one cares about and who, in turn, care about the person who cares. Hence, wellness involves a reciprocal relationship between the carer and others.

In this article, unlike Hettler's six interdependent dimensions of wellness and Stoewen's eight dimensions of wellness, we have reduced the number of dimensions of wellness to two key ones: (1) physical wellness and (2) mental wellness (as mentioned earlier above), which everyone is familiar. Under the nexus of physical-mental wellness, we propose four additional dimensions of wellness and they are as follows:

- (1) Cognitive wellness,
- (2) Conative wellness,
- (3) Affective wellness, and
- (4) Sensory wellness (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. The Nexus of Physical-Mental Wellness

These four additional dimensions of wellness under the nexus of physical-mental wellness are based on the CCAS model of the human potential with CCA (cognition, conation and affect) being first postulated by Poland (1974), and many years later, S (sensation) was added by Chia (2011) to the original CCA model to form the new CCAS model linking the C-C-A together by S (see Figure 4).

Figure 4. The CCAS Model

Briefly described, cogniton is defined as an "act of apprehending or ability to grasp or lay hold of mentally" (Chia, Kee, & Yusof, 2010, p. 9), and it consists of four mental parts:

- (1) Linguistic ability,
- (2) Mathematical ability,
- (3) Motor coordination ability, and
- (4) "Knowledge of self in response to somatic needs, and interaction with the environment at large to establish the knowledge of the world" (Chia, Kee, & Yusof, 2010, p. 9).

Next, conation is "that faculty of desiring or willing involving three self-explanatory parts: (1) self-awareness, (2) volition, and (3) self-regulation" (Chia, Kee, & Yusof, 2010, p. 9).

Next, affect refers to the emotional state that is associated with or causes an idea or an action, and it

overlaps with two conative aspects, i.e., self-awareness and self-regulation (see Chia, 2010a, 2010b, for more detail).

Finally, sensation is that binding force to hold the CCA together and ability to make meaningful sense of external and/or internal stimuli that will influence one's thinking (cognition), willing (conation) and feeling (affect).

Based on the CCAS model, we propose that the concept of wellness should be understood in terms of cognitive wellness, conative wellness, affective wellness and sensory wellness. For instance, a school-aged child who is unwell or unhealthy will experience a poor state of well-being to be educated or being educable. Hence, it is important to sustain the wellness of a child to be educable (process) in order to become educated (product). For this aspect, we have developed the informal Educated/Educable Child Rating Scale to measure the wellness of an educated/educable child.

The four dimensions of the CCAS-based wellness/health (see Figure 5) are briefly described below:

Figure 5. The CCAS-based Wellness Model

- (1) Cognitive wellness/health: This refers to the ability to clearly think, learn, and remember. It is an important component of performing everyday activities.
- (2) Conative wellness/health: This refers to the ability to avoid negative thinking, take various perspectives on an issue, interact responsibly with others, manage controversy and resolve conflict. It also develop goals and commitments (intentions and goals) to something akin to a stance, attitude, or disposition.
- (3) Affective wellness/health: This refers to the frequency and intensity with which a person experiences positive affect (PA) and negative affect (NA). PA and NA encompass both specific emotions and general mood states.
- (4) Sensory wellness/health: This is the wellness bridge connecting sensory processing and integration, and self-regulation, which allows a person to feel safe, confident, and in control. Ultimately, it gives the person a sense of well-being as an agent of change in the environment.

Essence of the CCAS-based Wellness

The essence of the CCAS-based wellness pertains to the condition of being happy, healthy, and prosperous. It does not only encompass physical and mental wellness/health but also cognitive, conative, affective and sensory wellness as an essential wholistic aspect of a fulfilling life. The importance of wellness cannot be overstated, as it affects every aspect of a person's lives, including relationship, productivity, and overall quality of life.

Adapted from Kutiyal's (2023) list of benefits of wellness, we have listed some reasons why the CCAS-based nexus of physical-mental wellness is important to everyone of

us (young and old):

(1) Improved physical wellness/health: This helps to promote a healthy lifestyle through regular exercise, balanced nutrition, and sufficient rest (Kutiya, 2023). Such positive practices can prevent chronic illnesses (e.g., diabetes, heart disease, and obesity).

(2) Enhanced mental wellness/health: This is crucial for one's well-being, i.e., if a person is mentally healthy, stress and anxiety can be coped/managed better, mood can improve, and a better quality of life is assured.

(3) Mindful cognitive wellness/health: This is essential in order to keep our mind alert and, in turn, also helps to keep the brain healthy. Playing board games and completing sudoku and crossword puzzles can help to keep the mind active or occupied, delaying the cognitive decline or impairment that often leads to dementia in old age.

(4) Better regulated conative wellness/health: This helps a person to keep an open mind, adopt a positive attitude toward life, and avoid negative thoughts (e.g., when one loses a job or falls very ill). In this way, one has a better grasp of self-regulation.

(5) Better affective wellness/health: This helps a person to build and maintain healthy relationships with those around him/her. S/He can become better equipped to express oneself by displaying empathy and understanding, interact effectively as well as establish meaningful rapport with others.

(6) Increased sensory wellness/health: A healthy mind-body (also known as noosoma where noos means 'mind' and soma refers to 'body') nexus requires good balanced sensory system in terms of sensory processing of internal as well as external stimuli, modulation of senses or sensory inputs/registration, and response/reaction to others as well as one's environment. This is essential for optimal living. When one feels good, s/he is more focused, efficient, and effective at work.

With an excellent CCAS-based wellness/health, a person can assured of an improved overall quality of life. Such wellness or "wellbeing can contribute to an overall sense of happiness, fulfillment, and satisfaction in life" (Kutiya, 2023, para. 24). When a person feels good physically, mentally, cognitively, conatively, affectively (or emotionally) and sensorily, s/he can enjoy his/her life to the fullest.

Conclusion

In conclusion, prioritising one's wellness is key to achieving one's optimal health and happiness. However, it is important to emphasize that this should be a continuous process requiring one to stay committed to the cause, put in effort to sustain and balance mindfulness-bodyfulness (i.e., self-awareness) one's all-inclusive wellness. By making small changes to one's daily habits, a person can significantly improve his/her overall well-being, and hopefully, lead a more fulfilling life which is described as salutogenesis – first coined by Antonovsky (197) – suggesting that a person possesses the innate capacity

to move toward health in the face of hardship.

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